

Expectations of usability aspects for human-robot interactions in manufacturing settings are changed by experience*

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Abstract—Personal experience is a major source of expectations which can influence subsequent behavior and judgement. In this paper, a virtually simulated human-robot-interaction (HRI) scenario was used to evaluate which usability aspects of the robotic system are expected most and how prior experience contributes to these expectations. With robots steadily becoming more frequent in today's work environments, incorporating users' expectations on the system's usability into the implementation process is of utmost importance to ensure an optimal quality of interaction. The study was conducted online to facilitate the distribution across multiple companies of the Italian Automobile Industry (N=430). Data on human-related and technical parameters were collected. For further analyses, participants were divided based on their level of experience. The results indicate that having prior experience (working) with robots changes the users' expectations for the system's usability. While a self-explaining design and suitability for the task is more valued by inexperienced users, the individualization of the systems is rated as more important when having prior experience. However, all participants valued the controllability of the system most. New robotic systems should therefore not only be developed in a way that it minimizes the need for learning and supports the discovery of its capabilities, but more so that the users maintain in control of the interaction. Moreover, the option to individualize the system should be available to everyone with prior experience to ensure ongoing acceptance of new technology.

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I. INTRODUCTION

In social psychology, it is widely agreed upon that expectations have an influence on how future situations are anticipated and can, therewith, shape the behavior of a person [1, 2, 3]. The confirmation bias and the self-fulfilling prophecy theory are key concepts that explain this effect. According to the self-fulfilling prophecy theory, individuals' expectations play a crucial role in shaping their reality [4]. On the other hand, confirmation bias leads people to seek out evidence that supports their existing expectations, further reinforcing those beliefs [5]. Olson et al. state that subjective experience, whether something was experienced as easy, difficult, pleasant or unpleasant, change how situations, objects or people are expected to be(have) [1]. More recently, social robots have been introduced into this line of research and it was found that similar patterns arise [6, 7]. On a broader level, the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) predicts that user expectations regarding system performance as well as the effort working with it can influence the user's behavioural intention to use a technology [8]. The level of experience moderates, according to Olson et al. [1], the theories of confirmation bias [5] and self-fulfilling prophecy [4] as well as the UTAUT model, the user's expectations and therewith influences the user's behavior. It is well established in scientific literature that these parameters, as a consequence, are fundamental to the overall quality of interaction [9, 10]. In the present study, these theoretical concepts are tested within an industrial human-robot interaction scenario, focussing on the interaction principles [11]. Although the percentage of companies that employ robots that interact directly with humans is still low (3.7%), small and medium-sized enterprises increasingly use

these emerging technologies. Especially in the manufacturing sector, human-robot interaction (HRI) applications become more and more frequent [12]. Within these hybrid working systems, human and robot cooperate to finish a working task or to achieve a certain goal [8, 13]. In general, they become more and more distributed in European workplaces, which brings a structural change into production work [14]. Additionally, due to high flexibility and configurability, they can reduce and even prevent occupational risks [15]. Consequently, this development has led to a more efficient and competitive production in Europe [16, 17]. However, an analysis by Riemer and Wischniewski [18] revealed that most online newspaper headlines on robots at work (for the year 2016 – 2018) had an overall negative tone. This stands in contrast to their potential to design work in a more human-centered way through a decrease of negative effects on mental and physical health. These negative reports could be used as a source of second-hand opinion which could then moderate the workers' expectations [1, 18, 19] or cause reluctance towards these robotic systems. Moreover, there is an increasing need to understand how these systems are perceived so the usability can be fostered since with higher acceptance and trust the misuse and disuse of a system can be decreased [8, 20]. This makes asking participants about their expectations regarding the system's usability a mandatory technology related parameter. This reasoning was also taken up by the European project SOPHIA (Socio-Physical Interaction Skills for Cooperative Human-Robot Systems in Agile Production). The aim of the project is to create innovative robotic technologies for cooperative human-robot systems (<https://project-sophia.eu/>). During one of its surveys, the expectations of workers in multiple manufacturing companies as well as their opinion on the usability of a hybrid working system (Fig. 1) were evaluated to optimize the implementation process of new robotic applications in real work environments. For this, the HTO framework provided a structure for the evaluation process [21]. It is constituted by three parts, the human (H), the technology (T) and the organization (O) which are interconnected by the working task. The framework provides a relevant basis for analyzing any socio-technical working system and emphasizes the workers' health and wellbeing, especially in human-technology interactions. Particularly in the manufacturing sector, it will be highly important to monitor the interaction quality during the implementation of new collaborative systems. The European Survey of Enterprises on New and Emerging Risks (ESENER) conducted by the European Agency for Safety and Health shows that most workers have been informed about possible impacts on health and safety like time pressure (59.3%) and need for continuous training (77.3%) [22]. These effects are strongly related to the interaction principles [11] of self-descriptiveness, learnability and controllability. The human factors and ergonomics (HFE) group at the Federal Institute of Occupational Health and Safety (BAuA) is in charge of

evaluating changes that come with the implementation of the developed technologies. For this, end-user and core-technology requirements as well as the assessment and evaluation of trust, interaction quality, expectations and usability in multiple use cases of the project were taken into account. The objective was to give recommendations on design specifications and evaluate changes in the workplace to ensure an effective interaction of humans with technology. As part of the project, different data was collected on the subject of usability aspects. To complement the existing dataset from the SOPHIA use cases and the industrial partners regarding the workers' expectations of interaction principles [23], this large-scale online study was conducted. Especially, it was aimed at evaluating which usability aspects of the robotic system yield the highest expectations and how prior experience shapes these expectations. Following the results of experiments in social psychology [1, 4, 5], it was hypothesized that novices and experts would differ in their expectations regarding the interaction principles. First, the study procedure and taken measures will be described, followed by a detailed analysis of differences in expectations between experienced and inexperienced participants. Then, the results will be presented, discussed and interpreted in the context of occupational health and safety.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Participants

The study was conducted online during six months, from December 2021 to May 2022 (N = 430) and was filed out by German (N = 69) and Italian (N = 361) participants from which 166 were female and 264 male. The mean age of the population was 45 years (SD = 11.6), with the oldest participant being 71 years old and the youngest 21.

B. Procedure

Due to the Covid-19 pandemic the study was published online on the platform SurveyCircle (<https://www.surveycircle.com/en/>). The website offers a large community for online research and is mostly frequented by students and active researchers that conduct studies themselves. Additionally, the link was directly forwarded to multiple companies from the Italian Automobile Industry and distributed internally. Here, potential participants were able to read a short description of the study and, if interested, they were redirected to another platform on which the actual survey took place (SosciSurvey). Subsequently, the questionnaire started with the gathering of sociodemographic information. Next, questions about prior experience and familiarity with robots were presented to the participants. Their media-related opinion towards robots as well as their general perception of the number of reports were assessed in the same questionnaire. Then, a video was shown that depicted an animated version of

a manufacturing use case scenario from the SOPHIA project (Fig. 1).

Here, a collaborative robot (CoBot) and a human work together on a heavy object. The robot picks it up from a container and takes it on its movable platform to another position in the assembly line. At the same time, the worker

deals with precision work on a different object and cleans it. The robot then moves the finished object to the correct container.

Fig. 1. Animated usecase scenario of a human-robot-interaction from the SOPHIA project

The presented video can be found under the following link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H-W0yy7LIA8>. After the participants watched the video, they were given the questionnaire on the expected quality of interaction regarding the system they had just seen. Since data acquisition was done through the German website and additionally via the Italian Automobile Industry, the questionnaires had to be translated from German into Italian by partners of the SOPHIA project. To ensure a solid process, a protocol documenting the process was provided: someone translated the Italian version back to English without knowing the English original which was then compared to the original and differences were identified, marked, and discussed so that the Italian translation could be adapted when necessary. The administration of the questionnaires in Italy took place thanks to an agreement between INAIL (Italian Workers' Compensation Authority) and ANFIA (Associazione Nazionale Filiera Industria Automobilistica – <https://www.anfia.it/it/>). The procedure for filling in the questionnaires was explained prior to participation in the study. For the whole evaluation process, data privacy requirements are met (according to the project's data protection concept) and an ethics approval of the BAuA's ethics commission, as well as from the Italian local ethics committee (N. 0078009/2021) was obtained.

C. Measures

Following the HTO framework [21], human and technological related parameters were considered. As human characteristics, and according to the findings that experience has the potential to influence user expectations [1, 4, 5], the participant's experience when working with robots ("I have a

lot of experience working with robots") as well as their familiarity with them ("I have often seen robots in real life") was assessed. Participants were additionally asked to reveal their age, gender and their level of education. Moreover, the collected data included the individual job sector as well as the company size and if they had a leading role in their job. Additionally, to assess the participants' opinion on media reports about robots in the context of work, three questions about the tonality of these reports were evaluated: positive, negative or neutral. Subsequently, they were asked if they believe that there are a lot of articles about this topic and how much media reports might influence people in their way of thinking about robotic systems. Altogether, this resulted in eight items that were structured so that participant could choose between six options from 1 "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree" and the option to choose "no idea". Next, technological affinity was assessed via a self-report, based on the Affinity for Technology (ATI) Scale [24] that measures the participants' usage behavior when technological innovations come forward. They could choose from five statements, beginning by being the first one to use a new technology to being rather skeptical and cautious about introducing them into their daily life. Regarding technological related parameters, the participants' expectations were assessed by presenting them statements about the seven ISO interaction principles (Table 1) which they had to rate on a 5-point scale from strongly disagree to strongly agree. This is a self-developed, shortend version based on the IsoMetrics questionnaire by Gediga [25] which was derived from the ISO standard 9241-110:2019 [11]. Each of the seven general design principles for system design is represented by a single item. Although the questionnaire was developed before 2020 and is therefore not in line with the current version of the ISO standard, it can still be used to understand the preferences of participants. In the end, participants were also asked to rate these principles from one, most important, to seven, least important.

TABLE I.
DESCRIPTION OF THE DESIGN PRINCIPLES FROM THE ISO 9241-110:2019

Suitability for the task	The user-system interactions are based on the task characteristics and support the completion of the task.
Self-descriptiveness	The interactive system presents appropriate information to make its capabilities and use immediately obvious to the user without unnecessary user-system interactions.
Controllability	The system allows the user to maintain control of the user interface and the interactions, including the speed and sequence and individualization of the user-system interaction
Conformity with user expectations	The system's behavior is predictable based on the context

	of use and commonly accepted conventions in this context.
Error tolerance	The interactive system assists the user in avoiding errors and in case of identifiable errors treats them tolerantly and assists the user when recovering from errors.
Suitability for individualization	The possibility of adapting the robot to the workers' needs and abilities.
Learnability	The system supports discovery of its capabilities and how to use it, minimizes the need for learning and provides support when learning is needed

III. ANALYSIS

For the data analysis, SPSS Statistics Version 29 was used. First, the frequencies of specific occupations within the data set were screened as well as the language in which the questionnaires were filled out. There were 69 completed questionnaires in German and 361 in Italian. Next, the participants' familiarity with robots and their experience of working with robotic systems were assessed by the statements: The two questions on experience were cumulated to create an overall experience score. Taking the paper by [28] as a basis, participants were divided by their level of experience: a participant was labelled as experienced when their score was above 3.0 (N = 236) and inexperienced with a score lower than 3.5 (N = 193). The means and standard deviations were calculated for the whole sample as well as for the group of experienced and inexperienced workers separately. To test if the expected system's usability could be predicted by either media related opinion or prior experience, a linear regression model was chosen. For this, the overall expected usability was calculated out of the answers on the seven dialogue principles, regarding the participants' general expectations for these kinds of systems, by adding their values and dividing the result by seven. 64 participants did not answer all questions about the interaction principles and were therefore not included in the further analysis of possible influences of mentioned variables on the expected usability. All calculations were done for the whole sample as well as for the divided one, comparing answers from inexperienced and experienced participants. Additionally, it was tested for the contribution of prior experience on all dialogue principles separately, using unpaired t-tests. In order to get insights about which aspect of the interaction with the shown robotic system was of most interest to the participants, the mean values of the ranked principles were calculated. From this, it was possible to assess differences in the rating between various principles through unpaired t-tests.

IV. RESULTS

The biggest group of participants were production workers (N = 211) which is not surprising, given the fact that all Italian participants were recruited via the automobile industry. The

second biggest group were people working in commercial and administrative jobs. Other job sectors were presented with only few participants, students being the biggest group with 49 people. Nearly two thirds of the production workers indicated to be experienced with robots (N = 136). Most of the remaining experienced people were part of the administrative job sector (65). In total, nearly half of the participants had experience with robots (Table 2). Within the whole sample, participants were more inclined to say that media reports of robots in the context of work were positive (M= 3.89, SD = 1.15) than negative (M = 3.14, SD = 1.5). However, participants strongly agreed on the fact that mass media can influence people in their opinion about robots (M = 4.17, SD = .96). Comparing experienced with inexperienced participants, it was visible that the former rated mass media reportage significantly more often as negative than the latter (t (427) = - 2.6, p < 0.01). There was neither a significant difference regarding the positive statements about reports, nor about the influence of reports on peoples' opinion.

TABLE II. PERCEPTION OF MASS MEDIA REPORTAGE

Group	Positive		Negative		Neither positive nor negative	
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Scale						
Experienced (N = 236)	4.15	1.01	3.31	1.64	3.69	1.47
Inexperienced (N = 193)	3.56	1.15	2.93	1.31	3.27	1.26
Whole Sample (N = 429)	3.89	1.15	3.14	1.51	3.5	1.39

TABLE III. COMPARISON BETWEEN EXPECTED USABILITY RATINGS FOR PRESENTED SYSTEM (MEANS AND STANDARD DEVIATIONS)

Interaction Principle	Experienced (N = 193)		Inexperienced (N = 177)	
	M	SD	M	SD
Scale				
Suitability for the task	4.27	0.67	4.36	0.7
Learnability	4.37	0.64	4.34	0.69
Self-descriptiveness	4.18	0.64	4.21	0.74
Controllability	4.29	0.71	4.22	0.91
Conformity with User Expectations	3.96	0.99	4.19	0.74
Error Tolerance	3.7	1.07	3.47	1.15
Individualization	4.02	0.8	3.86	0.93

The first measure of expected usability was targeted towards the presented cooperative robotic system. The following results show the participants' expectations for the presented system (Table 3). Participants in the present study had high expectations regarding the system's overall usability

($M = 4.11$, $SD = .56$). Although the results of the linear regression model showed that there was no significant

influence of prior experience on the overall usability score $R^2 = .07$, $F(1, 366) = 1.99$, $p = 0.16$, specific interaction principles differed significantly with the level of experience (Figure 2). Experienced participants valued the principle of Individualization ($t(366) = -1.73$, $p < 0.01$), Controllability ($t(366) = -.80$, $p < 0.01$) and Conformity with user expectations ($t(366) = -2.57$, $p < 0.01$) significantly more than inexperienced participants. Another factor that influenced the usability ratings was the perception of mass-media reportage. Participants, despite their level of experience, rated the system's usability higher, when their perception of mass-media was more positive ($R^2 = .13$, $F(1,175) = 24.96$, $p < 0.01$; $R^2 = .17$, $F(1,189) = 38.85$, $p < 0.01$). Another variable that influenced the participants' expectations was technological affinity ($R^2 = .01$, $F(1,366) = 6.754$, $p = 0.01$). A second measure of expected usability was the general ranking of the interaction principles from most important (1) to least important (7) (Table 4). Here, the principle of Controllability had the highest ranking ($M=3.45$, $SD = 1.65$), for experienced ($M=3.57$, $SD = 1.65$) as well as inexperienced participants ($M= 3.29$, $SD = 1.63$). The latter ranked Suitability for the task as second important ($M=3.49$, $SD = 2.29$). The lowest ranking was given to the principle of error tolerance ($M = 4.81$, $SD = 1.73$) which again was consistent in both groups ($M = 4.73$, $SD = 1.67$; $M = 4.88$, $SD = 1.78$). The ranking of both groups can be seen in the table below. The comparison of experienced and inexperienced participants

further showed that Individualization was the principle with the highest difference in mean value: experienced participants ($M= 4.4$, $SD = 2.02$), inexperienced participants ($M = 3.89$, $SD = 1.87$), albeit the unpaired t-test was not significant ($t(427) = -2.76$, $p = .06$).

Fig. 2. Comparison between the expected usability ratings for the presented system from experienced and inexperienced participants

TABLE IV. COMPARISON BETWEEN EXPECTED USABILITY RATINGS FOR ROBOTIC SYSTEMS IN GENERAL (MEANS AND STANDARD DEVIATIONS)

Rating of Interaction Principle	Experienced (N = 193)	Inexperienced (N = 177)
Most important	Controllability	Controllability
	Learnability	Suitability for the task
	Suitability for the task	Learnability
	Individualization	Self-descriptiveness
	Self-descriptiveness	Conformity with User Expectations
	Conformity with user expectations	Individualization
Least important	Error tolerance	Error tolerance

V. DISCUSSION

This study aimed at evaluating which usability aspects of robotic systems are expected most and how prior experience shapes these expectations. Specifically it was hypothesized that novices and experts would differ in their expectations regarding robotic systems. Since it was not aimed to evaluate this particular system but rather understand which principles are valued most by participants wh'n ge'urally confronted with them, the online assessment was not hindering. Most participants were experienced working with robots as it is common in production jobs. However, it is not clear why they were significantly influenced by their negative perception of mass media reportage while participants who are less familiar with robots are not. A possible explanation is that the contact they had with robots might have caused negative associations with these kinds of systems and therefore influenced their rating when confronted with one of them. This would fit to the fact that error tolerance was the least expected interaction principle and suggests that experienced users might not feel that errors can be easily recovered from. This would be a crucial issue for acceptance and the subjective feeling of safety and should be investigated further. Interestingly, the principle error tolerance was rated with the highest variance, meaning that it was not only often selected as least important but also as most important from other participants. This suggests that either there is a misunderstanding about the requested information or the topic is very controversial. Another unexpected finding was that participants agreed more to the statement that reports about robots in the context of work are positive. This is in contrast to the findings by Riemer and [18] who found that most media reports issued

between 2016 and 2018 were valued as negative. Possibly, further evaluation of article headlines in recent years would be a valuable source of information as the overall tonality of these reports might have changed with time. Additionally, when working with multicultural participants, a reference of headlines in other languages, in this case, Italian, would have been favorable to imply the importance of mass-media for the participants' opinion towards robots.

VI. CONCLUSION

The high number of experienced participants inside the manufacturing sector shows how widespread robotic systems already are in today's industrial workplaces. This is consistent with the results of the ESENER data analysis as it depicts the manufacturing sector as the most frequent one for human-robot interaction applications [12, 27]. The tonality of media reports was rated more on the positive than negative side for all participants and this perception influenced the usability ratings significantly. Additionally, a higher self-report on technical affinity also predicted a more positive expected usability rating. The overall expected usability was rather high and participants mostly expected the system to be easy to learn and controllable. This indicates that the feeling of control over the pace and sequence of the interaction is crucial for people working with robots. This parameter should therefore always be assessed when implementing human-robot interaction applications. However, the principle of individualization was significantly more important to experienced participants. The same holds true for conformity with user expectations. Participants with more experience give more importance to the specific functions that are important or maybe necessary to make this possible. This indicates that personal experience changes the expectations of workers towards a robotic system within an industrial case. This adds to existing research in the field of social robotics [6, 7] and is in line with theories of social psychology [1, 4, 5] and the UTAUT model. Moreover, it shows that an ongoing evaluation of the workers' expectations and the system's usability is valuable in maintaining good working conditions when aiming for a human-centered design. Participants least expected error tolerance from the system and self-descriptiveness, which can be seen as a warning sign for implementing these kinds of robotic systems. When workers do not rely on the machines because they do not expect them to be working correctly or, at least, not causing great harm when small errors are made, the acceptability of the systems might be impaired. This shows again that including workers in manufacturing jobs to participate in these kinds of surveys is fundamental to understand the challenges within a specific workplace. All in all, the study showed that having control when working with robots is the most important aspect, regardless of the level of experience. However, some aspects of the interaction change in importance when one becomes more experienced. Therefore,

the quality of interaction will most probably benefit from taking the person's experience level into account. Additionally, an opportunity to give feedback on the actual system's usability might facilitate to maintain good working conditions for all levels of experiences.

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